

Synthesis of *N*-Methylbutobarbitone-*N*-(methyl-2,3,4-tri-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucuronide) under Phase Transfer Catalysed Condition

BASHIR AHMAD* and J. W. POWELL

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, The School of Pharmacy, University of London,
29/39 Brunswick Square, London, WC1N 1AX U.K.

Manuscript received 18 April 1988, accepted 6 January 1989

N-Methylbutobarbitone-*N*-glucuronic acid (protected) was synthesised by a phase transfer catalysed reaction which was characterised by proton nmr and mass spectrometry (EI) to investigate the human metabolism of butobarbitone.

PHASE-II metabolism of most drugs and xenobiotics that make their way into the human body result in the formation of conjugates with the indigenous substances like glucose and glucuronic acids. The aqueous solubility of these conjugates make them easily excretable through the urine¹.

N-Glucosylation and glucuronidation of barbiturates, sulphonamides and other drugs have been reported² but the evidence for their precise structure of the proposed conjugates has not been supported by the modern analytical techniques like nmr and mass spectrometry. Synthesis of such required authentic conjugates in a pure state seems to be the major problem. The present paper describes successfully the synthesis of *N*-glucuronic acid (protected) conjugate of *N*-methylbutobarbitone by adaptation of a reported method³. The synthetic product was characterised by ¹H nmr and mass spectrometry (EI).

Experimental

N-Methylbutobarbitone-*N*-(methyl-2,3,4-tri-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucuronide) was synthesised³ by dissolving *N*-methylbutobarbitone (0.42 g, 0.002 mol) and benzyltriethylammonium bromide (0.28 g, 0.001 mol) in aqueous sodium hydroxide (1.25 *M*; 2 ml). The resulting solution was added to a solution of methyl 2,3,4-tri-*O*-acetyl- α -bromoglucuronate (0.41 g, 0.002 mol) in chloroform (5 ml). The mixture was stirred vigorously and heated under reflux for 3 h. After cooling, water (5 ml) was added. The chloroform layer was separated and washed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (1.25 *M*; 2 \times 3 ml) and dried (sodium sulphate). The solvent was removed to get a gummy material which on recrystallisation from aqueous methanol yielded the product (0.5 g, 50%), m.p. 49–53°.

Results and Discussion

Microanalysis was performed on a Carlo Erba 1106 analyser. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded on a Bruker WP 80 SY (80 MHzFT) spectrometer and mass spectra on a VG-Analytical ZAB-1F instrument with electron impact mode of ionisation. The product (Found: C, 53.3; H, 6.3; N, 5.0. C₂₄H₃₄N₂O₁₂ requires: C, 53.1; H, 6.2; N, 5.2%) revealed δ (CDCl₃) 0.9 (6H, t), 1.1–1.3 (4H, m), 1.9–2.2 (13H, m), 3.35 (3H, s), 3.85 (3H, s), 4.1–4.4 (1H, m), 5.2–5.5 (3H, m) and 6.15 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz); *m/z* (%) 483 (*M*-COOMe, 68), 423 (483-OAc, 13), 411 (16), 363 (423-OAc, 18), 321 (65), 227 (10), 171 (4), 155 (21), 127 (11), 113 (5), 97 (7), 83 (6), 69 (4), 55 (16) and 43 (Ac, 100).

The previous methods used for the synthesis of protected glucosides and glucuronides^{4,5} have generally resulted in rather low yields of the desired conjugates. The real advantage of the adapted method³ is that it involves a phase transfer technique, in which the protected bromosugar is held in the organic phase (chloroform), and in this way is somewhat protected from premature attack by the alkali. *N*-Methylbutobarbitone is dissolved in a slight excess of aqueous alkali, thus generating \ominus *N*-anion; this will then attack, nucleophilically, the bromoglucuronide (protected) when the two reactants are brought into intimate contact by the influence of benzyltriethylammonium bromide (a phase transfer catalyst) at the interface. The reaction product being lipophilic, will be distributed predominantly in the organic phase and will consequently be protected from hydrolytic breakdown by the residual alkali. Thus this simple method was found to give excellent yields of the required protected glucuronide conjugate.

The stereochemistry of the linkage at the glucuronide (protected) would be expected to be β , if the

* Present address: Department of Pharmacy, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan-60800, Pakistan.

attack by the N-methylbutobarbitone anion on the bromosugar had followed the SN₂ mechanism. That the link was actually β, was supported by the nmr analysis of the anomeric proton, which showed a doublet at δ 6.15 (J 9 Hz); these values are consistent with the expected β-glucuronide linkage⁴.

N-Glucoside (protected) of the same barbiturate was also synthesised⁶.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the British Council for the award of a Study Fellowship, and to W. C. Baldeo, D. Carter and K. Welham at The School of Pharmacy, for their technical assistance.

References

1. G. J. DUTTON, "Glucurodination of Drugs and other Compounds", CRS Press, Florida, 1980.
2. B. K. TANG, W. KALOW and A. A. GREY, *Res. Commun. Chem. Path. Pharm.*, 1978, **21**, 45; M. P. WYTHE and A. S. DEKABAN, *Drug Metab Disp.*, 1977, **5**, 63; D. E. DUGGAN, J. J. BALDWIN, B. H. ARISON and R. E. RHODES, *J. Pharm. Exp. Ther.*, 1974, **190**, 563; J. W. BRIDGES and R. T. WILLIAMS, *Biochem. J.*, 1962, **83**, 27; J. W. BRIDGES, M. R. KIBBY and R. T. WILLIAMS, *Biochem. J.*, 1965, **96**, 829; J. W. BRIDGES, S. R. WALKER and R. T. WILLIAMS, *Biochem. J.*, 1969, **111**, 173; T. UNO and M. URDA, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1963, **11**, 709; F. F. KADLUBAR, J. A. MILLER and E. C. MILLER, *Cancer Res.*, 1977, **37**, 805; R. G. SMITH, G. D. DAVES, R. K. LYNN and N. GERBER, *Biochem. Mass Spectrom.*, 1977, **4**, 275; J. L. WOOLEY and C. W. SIGEL, *Drug Metab. Disp.*, 1979, **7**, 94; R. D. G. WOOLFENDEN in "Analytical Profiles of Drug Substances", ed. K. FLOREY, Academic, New York, 1977, Vol. 6; P. NIELSEN, *Biochem. J.*, 1973, **136**, 1039; G. D. PAULSON, J. M. GIDDING, C. H. LAMOUREUX, E. R. MANSAGER and C. B. STRUBLE, *Drug Metab. Disp.*, 1981, **9**, 142; J. E. MATUSIK, C. J. BARNES, D. R. NEWKIRK and T. FAZIO, *J. Assoc. Off. Anal. Chem.*, 1982, **65**, 828; D. D. GIERA, R. F. ABDULLA, J. L. OCCOLOWITZ, D. E. DORMAN, J. L. MERTZ and R. F. SIEK, *J. Agric. Food. Chem.*, 1982, **30**, 260.
3. D. DESS, H. P. KLEINE, D. V. WEINBERG, R. J. KAUFMAN and R. S. SIDHU, *Synthesis*, 1981, **13**, 889.
4. B. K. TANG, W. KALOW and A. A. GREY, *Drug Metab. Disp.*, 1979, **7**, 315.
5. M. A. M. AL-SHARIPI, Ph. D. Thesis, London, 1982; R. J. STUBBS, Ph. D. Thesis, London, 1982; W. H. SOINE, V. O. BHARGAVA and L. K. GARRETTSON, *Drug Metab. Disp.*, 1984, **12**, 792; B. BERRANG, C. E. TWINE, G. L. HENNESSY and F. I. CARROLL, *Synth. Commun.*, 1975, **5**, 281.
6. B. AHMAD and J. W. POWELL, Unpublished results.